

Determinant of shopping motivation and their influence towards fashion retailers, with the mediating role of fashion innovations and fashion consciousness

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Abstract:

Adjusting and stimulating the fashion purchases within fashion stores the challenging situation of market strength to discover the new ways in fashion industry for introducing the new products. The study is based on four determinants of shopping motivation which are Sexual Attraction, Shopping for Recreation, Recognition Enhancement, Aesthetic Expression. Fashion consciousness and fashion innovativeness have strategic position in this challenge. In the setting of fashion retailing this study inspects how fashion consciousness and fashion innovativeness relates with factors of shopping motivation and actual fashion purchasing. It also examines the construct of shopping motivation on the association among fashion innovativeness, fashion consciousness and fashion purchases. The study executed through a consumer survey, data were obtained and analyzed using structural equation modelling. The consequences show that shopping motivation is positively affected by fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness, and positively influences fashion purchase intention of customers. The direct link between shopping motivation and fashion purchase intention shows insignificant result. By using the concept of fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness this study delivers recommendations for fashion retailers on increasing fashion purchases in their stores.

Keywords: Shopping motivation, fashion innovativeness, fashion consciousness, purchase intention, fashion retailers

Introduction:

A multi-million dollar fashion industry and international companies committed to the creation, design and selling of customer clothing (Chun, Lim, Tan, & Teh, 2018). Researchers also clarified that it could demonstrate in a way that retailers of clothing and accessories are aligned with the global industry. It can be proven that the fashion industry plays an important role in society today. Now, you use fashion for self-identification as a way of expressing yourself. The fashion industry has changed gradually globally, and is highly globalized. Consumers are more competitive and markets are becoming more unpredictable, leading to retailers working harder to continue growing (Anić, Mihić, & Kursan Milaković, 2018). Brand improvements and customer acceptance are important to success in this challenging environment. New products are often not adopted by customers and retailers are effective in stimulating purchases; therefore, they need to better understand how consumers react and embrace fashionable clothing (Anić et al., 2018).

Fashion Innovativeness or fashion consciousness is a key concept in consumer behavior, a theory commonly used to investigate the mechanism of fashion diffusion and brand victory. It may be characterized as the tendency of consumers to buy new products of fashion, and the extent to which consumers are prepared to take new ideas relatively earlier than other social systems members (Cardoso, Costa, & Novais, 2010; Im, Bayus, & Mason, 2003; Rogers, 1995). Customer who are one of the earliest to take on new items of fashion are called innovators of fashion. Fashion innovators are a valued retail division because they generate enough income and control the acceptance and distribution of fashion within a social group (Goldsmith & Stith, 1993; Jordaan & Simpson, 2006). The success of fashion retailers depends largely on the fast reflection of a constantly changing fashionable appetite for consumers and their newest fashion trends. Fashion retailers therefore need to build an effective communication network for customers to integrate their feedback into the various product development processes (Gruner & Homburg, 2000). An increasing number of retailers are trying to build customer contact and engaging, such as customization (Ricotta & Costabile, 2007), customer co-creativity and marketing reversals, have now been, which is now part of a new chant, particularly in the fast-running retail industry.

The goal of this study was to develop a theoretical model that identifies how customer involvement in the product development process increases satisfaction and subsequently develops purchase intention in the context of fashion retailing. The aims of the research are in Faisalabad known as the textile city of Pakistan. In addition, a recent survey has shown the important impact on customer perceptions in the sense of fashion co-creation on personal characteristics (Wu, Kim, Chen, & Johnson, 2017), Our knowledge of how product attributes like fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness are still constrained in shaping the customer-retailer relationship. The research also looks into the potential impact of consumer shopping motivation in order to address the gap in our literature in relation to fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness in relation to customer purchase intention. Particularly, there is no study could be found in context of Pakistan. This study's aim is to fill the research gaps concerning determinants of shopping motivation, fashion innovativeness, fashion consciousness and purchase intentions for fashion apparels.

Literature Review:

Purchase Intention:

Purchase intent could be described as the intention of individuals to buy a certain product they have chosen and preferred after a specific assessment (Khuong & Nguyen, 2015). As according to (Vineyard, 2014), the purchase intention is an opportunity to purchase products and services. The intention to purchase a product or brand is one of the customer cognitive behavior (Hosein, 2012). Intention to purchase is also the concept of future purchases (Goyal, 2014). Good customer ad response can have an intended impact on their purchase (Lafferty, Goldsmith, & Newell, 2002). And it is an important element in measuring fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness and mediates in the relationship between the shopping motivation and the consumer purchasing intention developing attitude. There is a direct link between the shopping motivation and fashion innovativeness (Kapoor & Munjal, 2019). Consumers will first collect their preference, practice and feedback from others and then adopt the alternative assessment process and finally take purchase decisions (Chi, Yeh, & Tsai, 2011). Blogs have been used by retail and company to advertise their apparels (Jacob, 2013). In 2013, In 2013, the clothing business partnered in establishing a forum with the influencers of fashion bloggers (Rickey, 2013).

Fashion consciousness:

Fashion consciousness, could be described in one's appearance which characterized by an interest in fashion and clothing (Gutman & Mills, 1982; Summers, 1970), is often described as possessing a code (O'Cass, Jin Lee, & Siahtiri, 2013). Fashion apparel practices are also recognized as a way for individuals to articulate their identity and image (Michaelidou & Dibb, 2006) and their social identity (Entwistle, 2015). Fashion consciousness for fashion retailers is an essential aspect as it affects consumers' personal traits to be more open and to make use of fashion marketer interaction (Kaiser & Chandler, 1984; Kinley, Conrad, & Brown, 1999). Fashion consciousness could be described as the extent to which people can appreciate clothing and fashion apparel (Nam et al., 2007). It represents up to date personal value for maintaining social status (Lertwannawit & Mandhachitara, 2012). Generally, the literature underpins that consumers with a greater degree of fashion consciousness have differences in the processing of information (for example, knowledge search), beliefs and attitudes towards apparel, and that responses are carried out by brands with a lower degree of fashion consciousness (Naderi, 2013). The knowledge of fashion, though, is never focused solely on women again. Men who are knowledgeable of fashion are gradually happy with their own identities. In having fashionable apparels, men show themselves to be confident with both their private and their social image (Gould & Stern, 1989). As more high-profile buyers are remunerated for their fashion consciousness, they are leaders in developing their consciousness towards appearance and fashion. Keeping alert and mindful of trend does not necessarily mean purchasing fashionable apparels. Those with little knowledge of fashion shopping were giving no interest or time (Bakewell, Mitchell, & Rothwell, 2006). The actions of people who aren't informed of fashion conscious to make shopping more convenient (Workman & Cho, 2012). In fact, in the framework of Pakistan very few researches examined the fashion consciousness (Khan, Fatima, & Matloob, 2019). Thus, hypothesize:

H: Fashion consciousness will mediate the relationship between shopping motivation and Purchase intention

Consumers who know how to updated with the new fashion and are able to shop for themselves (Walsh, MITCHELL, & Hennig-Thurau, 2001). You were more likely to talk about fashion with friends and see that this is a recognized source of information (Afonso Vieira, 2009; Nam et al.,

2007). Will in general assess the quality all the more seriously by utilizing different signals (Gitimu, Workman, & Robinson, 2013). They are regularly buying different types of fashion apparel items; spend some more time and money to shop as compared with the individuals those are less-fashion conscious (Fairhurst, Good, & Gentry, 1989; Flynn & Goldsmith, 1993). Customers of various style rates change their responses to the characteristics of the clothing item, and thus have different ways of dealing with apparels (Kim, Lynn Damhorst, & Lee, 2002). A close correlation has been observed between the understanding of style and fashion, which may contribute to the highest degrees of customer trust in fashion decisions (O'Cass, 2004).

Fashion Innovativeness:

There were existing theory outcomes proposed that customer purchasing behavior has been influenced by shopping motivation (Buttle, 1992). There were several factors that were shown to touch customers in the fashion choice for instance the want for acceptance and appreciation. The objective of various related activities in which the inspired customers were willing and ready to purchase a product (Tovikkai & Jirawattananukool, 2010), sexual attraction as well as recreation motivation (Chen-Yu & Seock, 2002). Thus, hypothesize:

H: Fashion consciousness will mediate the relationship between shopping motivation and purchase intention

(González & Bovone, 2012) recommends that apparel items might promote sexual consciousness and attraction between people, additionally, the ability of fashion that they can also illustrate and render more appealing the distinctions among men and women (Hausman, 2000) come to an understanding that in term of attractiveness, clothes are an essential component among people, and it is highlights that hedonic motives could be satisfies by shopping for apparels, such as the novelty, and variety, need for fun, which were all additionally found in different studies (Goldsmith & Stith, 1993). (Epuran, Gârdan, Gârdan, & Bumbas, 2015) Identify the variables affecting hedonic use and emphasize how necessary it is for clothes to be worn for their esthetic appearance (Birtwistle & Tsim, 2005) to illustrate that mature women find that clothing serves as the manifestation of their personality (Jordaan & Simpson, 2006). Even though several customer motives for buying apparel items were acknowledged, less is thought about shopping motives that influence fashion innovativeness.

Shopping Motivations:

The study has developed the notion of shopping motivation by (Chen-Yu & Seock, 2002; Shchudro, 2011). Utilizing the discoveries of (Chen-Yu & Seock, 2002), (Shchudro, 2011) identified the following construct of apparel shopping motivation: recreation, sexual attraction, conformity, aesthetic expression, recognition, enhancement, need and fashion expression. Apparel decisions are strongly affect by customers' desire to attain their targets. The research also shows similar motives for buying. Fashion changers want to attract others by using clothes and appearances; they have always been more aware of their presence and their bodies than their fashion followers (Park, Cho, & Rudd, 1999). In fact, apparel could raise sexual consciousness (González & Bovone, 2012). On the basis of these definitions it is necessary to assume beneficial association to sexual attraction, fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness. In addition, people termed as experimental fashion innovators indicated a high attention in fashion, enjoyed shopping and spending more on apparels (Cardoso et al., 2010), and more trips connected to apparels (Bruner, 1986). These customers observed shopping as a kind of amusement (Studak & Workman, 2004), and unlike the followers of fashion that embody a pragmatic (or need based) approach to the recognition of fashion problems, a psychological (or need based) approach is defined to fashion problems (Workman & Studak, 2006). Therefore, shopping motivation would have a significant impact on the fashion innovativeness and the fashion consciousness (Beaudoin, Moore, & Goldsmith, 2000) Specifies that fashion transition practitioners have more social status, reputation, and symbolic elements of fashion than fashion followers. The research of (Workman & Lee, 2011) do not validated these variations. Nevertheless, it has been build up that, not at all like fashion followers; fashion agents require differentiation and individuality more prominent (Stanforth, 1995; Workman & Caldwell, 2007; Workman & Kidd, 2000). Moreover, (Cardoso et al., 2010), as well as (Szczepaniak, 2015), withdraw a few fragments of customers which are subject to fashion engagement, impulsiveness, fashion innovativeness, and self-expression through fashion product, create an invention for 'enthusiasts' and convey what needs to be through fashion. Given the way in which specific characteristics and the acknowledgement of self-expression are defined by a shopping motivation that relies on a willingness to improve popularity, this motivating factor may be very well known to influence fashion consciousness and fashion innovativeness. In general, fashion is very concerned about

their fashion and appearance (Miller & Cox, 1982), and more beauty control practices relative with fashion followers (Park et al., 1999). Thus, hypothesize:

H: Shopping motivation has a direct positive effect on purchase intention

Research Model:

Methodology:

For the purpose of this study, the antecedents of shopping motivation towards fashion consciousness of fashion apparel were tried to be revealed. These dynamics of shopping motivation with the mediating role of fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness intent for fashion apparel were felt under-researched in the consumer markets of Pakistan. The quantitative technique of research was opted when data is collected in numeric format and different statistical techniques are implanted to analyze the data. Research instrument for data collection was well-built questionnaire comprising of different close-ended questions to measure ultimate dependent, as questionnaire is one of the most widely used research instrument used by the researchers. The data were collected from the specifically from fashion apparel consumers. The consumers who were available physically to shop real time from the markets where fashion apparel are found abundantly. Sample size of this study was 300. Three hundred consumers were accessed to fill in the questionnaires. Few of those were reporting missing values, which were

discarded later on. In the last, 219 questionnaires were found useful yielding a response rate of 73%.

The figures from the survey show that 75.3% of participants were males and 24.7% were females. Whereas around 50.2% of participants indicated that their average monthly income is up to forty thousand, 35.2 percent respondent income fall between 40 to 70 thousand, 9.6 percent respondent monthly average income fall in the category of 70 to 100 thousand, 5.0 percent responded having more than 100 thousand monthly average income.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of respondents:

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	165	75.3
Female	54	24.7
Total	219	100.0
Age in Years	Frequency	Percentage
20 to 30	61	27.9
31 to 40	108	49.3
41 to 50	48	21.9
Above 50	2	.9
Total	219	100.0
Education	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelors	119	54.3
Masters	68	31.1
MS/Mphil	27	12.3
PhD	5	2.3
Total	219	100.0
Average Income (PKR)	Frequency	Percentage
Upto 40 thousand	110	50.2
40 to 70 thousand	77	35.2
70 to 100 thousand	21	9.6
More than 100 thousand	11	5.0
Total	219	100.0

Notes: *PKR stands for Pakistani rupee.

Measurement Items of the Constructs:

All scales were measured by Likert-scale items ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The scales were adopted from the previous studies, to measure shopping motivation nine items scales were taken from (Chen-Yu & Seock, 2002; Shchudro, 2011). Fashion

innovativeness was estimated utilizing the area explicit innovativeness scale that was developed by (Goldsmith & Hofacker, 1991) and modified by numerous researchers, including (Mathur, Barak, & Zhang, 2009). The research constructs were measured with the help of multi-item scales comprising terminal and instrumental values adapted, to measure Fashion consciousness, scales were adopted from (Gould & Stern, 1989; Mulyanegara, 2011; Wan, Youn, & Fang, 2001). To measure Purchase intention, 4 items scales were taken from (Dodds, Monroe, & Grewal, 1991).

Results:

Table 2: Construct Reliability and Validity:

Variables	Items	Cronbach's	Composite	AVE
Shopping Motivation (SM)	4	0.749	0.841	0.570
Fashion Innovativeness (FI)	3	0.750	0.858	0.669
Fashion Consciousness (FC)	4	0.708	0.818	0.532
Purchase Intention (PI)	3	0.761	0.862	0.676

The reliability and validity table shows that there are four variables in this study from which the theoretical model was achieved. As mentioned in the table, the cronbach's values are 0.749, 0.750, 0.708 and 0.761 respectively. The value is acceptable when the value is greater than 0.6. The benchmark value for the Composite Reliability is 0.6. The values are 0.841, 0.858, 0.818 and 0.862 correspondingly. All the above values are greater than 0.6. For that reason, all variables are acceptable presenting that model is trustworthy. Benchmark value for AVE is 0.4. The values are 0.570, 0.669, 0.532 and 0.676 respectively. No value has been found less than 0.4; Consequently, all variables are considerable showing that model is acceptable & reliable.

Table 3 Total Effects:

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
FC -> PI	0.319	0.325	0.067	4.734	0.000
FI -> PI	0.049	0.050	0.072	0.690	0.491
SM -> FC	0.372	0.385	0.073	5.122	0.000
SM -> FI	0.350	0.361	0.064	5.491	0.000
SM -> PI	0.298	0.308	0.060	4.950	0.000

**p < 0.01 *p < 0.05 *p < .10

The above table presented the relations of (FC) and (PI) is highly significant with mean of 0.325. The (bootstrapping standard error), value is 0.067. The next value showed the relationship among (FI) and (PI) insignificant with mean of 0.050. The standard-error, value is 0.072. The next value explained the relationship among (SM) and (FC) is highly significant with mean of 0.385. The standard error, value is 0.073. The next display relationship among (SM) and (FI) is highly significant with mean of 0.361. The standard error, value is 0.064. The next value showed relationship among (SM) and (PI) is highly significant with mean 0.308. The standard-error, value is 0.060.

Direct effect of Path Estimates:

This model shows a strong positive path estimate with the value of (0.350) from (SM) to (FI). Next variables also showed a strong positive (0.372) path estimate from (SM) to (FC). The other variable shows the positive path estimation with the value of (0.049) from (FI) towards (PI). This

model showed a strong positive path estimate from (FC) to (PI) with the value of (0.319). All most, all the variable show significant.

Conclusion of the study

This examination ends the gap in past research by looking at how fashion innovation and fashion consciousness are related to shopping motives in the Pakistani fashion store. The consequences indicate that behind clothing shopping, sexual attraction, recreation, recognition and aesthetic expression are the main consumers ' motivations. The shopping motivations affect fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness significantly and favorably. In other terms, individuals purchasing attractive apparel (esthetic expression), The attraction towards opposite gender (sexual attraction), shopping for pleasure (shopping for recreation), and tend to be higher fashions innovativeness and fashion consciousness and express themselves different from others (recognition enhancement). New clothing products are probably accepted by such consumers. This study shows also that a person's personal and beautiful expression stimulates shopping for apparels and therefore stimulates fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness (Birtwistle & Tsim 2005; Jordaan & Simpson 2006).

Because fashion innovators are involved in shopping and fashion, as well as apparel (Kang & Johnson,2009) and have strong influence on fashion followers' buying actions (Birtwistle & Moore, 2006), knowing their interests and motivations is important for fashion producers and retailers. In addition, appropriate fashion facilities are essential and the fashion and stimulating shopping atmosphere accordingly. Retailers prerequisite to present new fashion product frequently and try to respond to the consumer's specific motivations to buy and sell foreseen product. A mixture of extravagant, easily recognizable and sexually attractive clothes should be offered in the retail industry. Advertising must emphasis and strengthen features of improved recognition, recreational shopping, sexual attraction and aesthetic expression. Thus, it is very well and useful for retail stores to boost entertainment and deliver a positive feeling and good mood environment. The results of this study may contribute to several strategic consequences. As Pakistan's consumers have low disposable income, Pakistani firms must not only cope with low income, they must also take innovative speculation to ensure their status in the wake of the Pakistan fashion industry's economic crisis. This research shows that fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness are important managerial variable and driver of purchase intention.

Limitation and future direction of study

The study is limited to future research in Pakistan that could analyze mediators in different regions and nations. In consumer decision-making, places where fashionable apparels are being acquired assume a key role. This has not been studied in this review; thus, future research may inspect the effect of fashion innovativeness, fashion consciousness and purchase intention on various store formats, Specialty stores and discount stores, such as department stores. The findings can also be related with performance data from retailers. In addition, future research may focus on multi-group investigation that can map consumer fragments inside the fashion framework. In terms of demographic and socio-economic characteristics, it could be fascinating to capture the association among shopping motivation, fashion innovation and fashion consciousness in various consumer groups. The findings of this study give, given the established shortcomings, important insights into fashion innovativeness and fashion consciousness behavior, just as some important managerial implications and bearings for further research.

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